

GENDER INEQUALITIES AND LANGUAGE EXPRESSION IN EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This research is aimed to research the difficulties in using a language by men and woman is just caused by their sexual differences. The factor shows that the factor of language expression is more important and determines how man and woman should speak. There are, at least factors that influence in transforming the difference of language expression that is domination or power, the different way of treating men or woman, and socialization, because of these factors, we find out some expression in English language, which represent gender inequalities; e.g. asymmetric marked and unmarked term, and semantically derogation.

Key Word: Language Expression, gender and education.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Language is tool of communication used to expresses the ideas at society. Language expression described speaker socialization. It also explains about the environment of social aspect, for example: social level, social act and environment. Chomsky stated that language is asocial because the society ignored the heterogeneities, in one side he chooses the language and in another side, he chooses the culture. To learn the language which relate with the social culture will produce four probabilities: First, social structure can influence, determine language act and structure. Second, language act and structure can influence and determine social structure. Third, the relationship of both of them is flash back. Fourth, Social culture and language structure does not have relationship.

If we took the first probability, so the language is the result of social consensus. The consensus is influence to the owner domination because they have a power to determine the rules. In Indonesian language, have a lingual item to express the differences about biologists, sexist, such as phoneme /a/ for masculine gender and /i/ for feminine gender. So, to look the differences using the language between masculine and feminine is too difficult, and is only in biologist. The result of research relate to the masculine language is too much, it is also different with the feminine language. Holmes stated that Indian Language, in South America, some of the words used by masculine have the taller sound than feminine.

Language discrimination occurred in all the practical of language, the condition makes the woman dilemma and it also caused two aspect discrimination, they are how they learned to use the language, and how the language treated. The advantages of the language for the masculine stresses to the feminine, except the English language with patriarchal ideologist determine by the man and give

the effect to the woman, although one word shows lower level for the woman such as feminine, euphemistic, and more powerless.

Based on that statement, it explains that the English language is patriakhal for the woman image. For example, to describe the old woman have eight utterances: hen, teat, hailer, war hose, chrome, hag, beldam and frump that explain if the woman utterance the object when speak the English language. This writing discussed about the language expression and stated that there is not the people justification to use the English language. It also describes about sex and gender, amities representation, siestas discourse, the difference of language and why that caused the differences gender language.

2. GENDER AND SEX DESCRIPTION

Every people birth in the world have become two sexualities, they are man and woman. Both of them have the differences in biologist capabilities. Basically the man has given attitude. Gender represents the differences categories between man and the woman must based on social culture constitution. It relates with status attitude, position, and roles in gender society and it also make the differences as a cultural social construction.

To give illustrated differences between gender and sex, it looked from the example of *Pancal* bicycle design. *Pancal* bicycle design made for the woman usually wider because the woman have the bigger figure (sexist differences), and the bicycle design to make easier drives for the woman who used the skirt. It is change the gender differences. So, sexual language is a language present by man and woman does not based on the level. It also serves stereo tripe about man and woman and it caused the woman unlucky.

3. SEXIST IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

The sexist language have two point of view, they are: first, about how far to handle the language grammatical, and second, to know how far the roles contribute of sexist English language grammatical system. There are some examples:

a. Symmetry and Asymmetry Problem

The English word includes to symmetry is the generic word “horse”, to speak gentle or feminine horses. Look these examples:

Example 1 : generic : horse
Betina : Mare
Jantan : Stallone
Anak kuda : Foal (jantan dan betina)
Anak kuda betina: Filly
Anak kuda jantan: colt

The term to speak about the people also uses some system, but there are not symmetries.

Example 1 : generic : man
Wanita : woman

Laki-laki : men

Anak-anak : child

Anak perempuan: girl

Anak laki-laki : boy

The word man and woman at second example shows clearly if there are bias meaning. In English language text, the word man means generic for all people and man have specific meaning. It different with this sentence: The man without faith has no sources, and the man is mean laki-laki.

Example 3 : Wanita : Miss/Mrs./MS

Laki-laki : Mr.

In English Language, for adult man only has one called, it is Mr. (mister), while for the woman detail identity, when she is a single, call her Miss and when she got married, call her Mrs. And Ms. Is the call for the woman if there is not clearly identity or bias (marriage or not) and is different for the man, we call him before and after marriage only have one called is Mr. The language treatment system like this clearly. Actually, Miss dominates called to use woman status.

b. The Signal and Not Signal Terms

There are the terms to differentiate the man and woman, and also there are the signal and not signal terms, that means for all the identity. For the signal used to show profession of the woman and usually give *-es* at the end of word.

Example 4 : Laki-laki Perempuan

God Goddess

Hosts Hostess

Actor Actress

Wait Waitress

Meanwhile, the word for not signal term and used to the man and woman, but at the fact user connotation for man such as the words professor, surgeon, doctor, etc. So, there is the perception for that professor is suitable only for man, and if there is profession only for a woman called nurses and for the man called male nurse. Those terms have the implication if the man position in one profession is more normal.

c. The Lowest and Smallest Meaning Connotation

The smallest meaning means the word refers to the woman has smallest than the man, while the woman has lowest connotation meaning. For examples:

Laki-laki Perempuan

Gentleman/lord Lady

d. The Tittle and Frequency of Speaking

The woman is talking active in society culture of patriarchal level of language. Actually stereotype about the differences of language style between man and the woman is only the prediction. The bigger stereo type is the woman speak dominant, although the prediction is not always true.

4. THE EFFECT OF SEXIST LANGUAGE

The society paradigm for the woman is only predicted the complement and object. The factors caused:

- a. The domination Problem : Based on the language research relate with social phonetic life and society culture, have been seen the woman is different with man.

- b. The differences problem : The differences problem caused the domination in one side to another side and birth the stigma if the woman is the object of the culture, while the man have seen the regulated the other people.

5. CLOSED

The conclusion based the explanation above is the language expression is represent the speaker attitude in English society, we can see the discrimination to the woman in language variation. The Stereo type happen when the man dominant in all sector to use the language, and another factor is the differences the homogeneity relation problem and it caused the effect of sub culture.

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